

Review

Institutional Enablers of ESG Adoption in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Systematic Review of Sustainable Corporate Governance and Firm Performance

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Abstract: *The review explores how institutional factors impact upon the uptake of Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) practices in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) and examines the link between ESG implementation and firm performance. In accordance with the PRISMA 2020 guidelines, 6 peer-reviewed empirical and review articles, published between 2020 and 22 June 2025, were identified and synthesized with a systematic data extraction and thematic analysis using the Theory, Context, Characteristics, Methodology (TCCM) framework. The thematic analysis indicates that governance structures especially board independence and regulatory oversight are the most important institutional drivers of ESG adoption and firm-level outcomes. Additionally, meta-analytic results show a significant positive effect of ESG on firm performance ($r = 0.287$, 95% CI [0.146, 0.418]). The between-study heterogeneity in this meta-analysis was low, $I^2 = 0\%$. However, environmental and social dimensions remain underdeveloped. This study offers a critical point of reference for the contextual understanding of ESG in African markets. Further rigorous and multi-level studies are needed to examine firm-level practices and broader policy contexts using a range of research methodologies. This is among the first studies to combine systematic review and meta-analytic techniques to evaluate ESG adoption in sub-Saharan African (SSA) context.*

Keywords: *ESG; Sustainable Corporate Governance; Firm Performance, Sub-Saharan Africa; Institutional Drivers; Systematic Review.*

1. Introduction

In recent years, the relevance of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) factors in shaping corporate strategy and performance has gained increasing traction globally and more recently, within Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). Against a backdrop of growing concerns around sustainability, corporate accountability, and institutional resilience, organisations are increasingly embracing ESG frameworks not only as a case for compliance but also as tool for strategic action (Kogi et al., 2025; Kimilu, 2021). The ESG landscape in SSA is defined by fragmented regulatory structures, varying institutional capacities and dissimilar firm level engagements; leading to relevant questions about what indeed drives ESG adoption and how such practices translate into firm-level performance.

While significant research progress has been made on ESG literature in emerging and developed economies (Seow, 2024; Manani & PS, 2025), it is almost certain that the institutional context of SSA creates unique challenges and different opportunities. In some of these regions, the social and governance aspects of ESG may be different from that of the developed countries. Regulatory environments differ across regions, with countries such as South Africa and Nigeria having noticeably strong regulatory frameworks than other frontier markets that have more nascent disclosure environments (Karaye, 2024; Gumbo, 2024). These institutions and resources affect the extent to which ESG principles are integrated within organisations and countries thereby being perceived as strategic assets, a source of investor pressure and part of the evolution of governance principles (Lu et al., 2022; Yong et al., 2024). Research has identified institutional drivers, including board diversity, legal infrastructure, stakeholder expectations and international reporting standards, as vital enablers or obstacles of ESG implementation (Xu et al., 2025; Al-Faryan, 2024). Nevertheless, empirical evidence in SSA is scant and disparate, mainly examining ESG from unitary dimensions or as sector-specific case studies (Cho & Wachira, 2022; Obol, 2023). Also, evidence on the ESG adoption-firm performance nexus, measured by profitability, market value or societal impact, is contradictory due to inconsistent contexts and methodologies (Abu-Ali et al., 2024; Nogueira et al., 2025).

Recent evidence from other emerging markets provides some useful comparative perspectives on these dynamics. In the case of ASEAN, for example, Mansour et al. (2025) found that board effectiveness, gender diversity, and environmental committee was associated with a higher likelihood of the carbon emission disclosure of listed companies in the region, and therefore, concluded that high governance quality can substitute for regulative forces and directly incentivize non-simulative sustainability reporting. In the study of 15,496 Asian firms, Saleh et al. (2025) reported that good ESG practices reduce corporate risk, and that there was a moderation effect of board gender diversity in the ESG–corporate risk relationship, using the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) model designed to address endogeneity between ESG and corporate performance. These cases illustrate the usefulness of dynamic governance mechanism and greater methodological sophistication in better assessing the ESG-performance link.

From a governance standpoint, the lessons from ASEAN markets offer useful analogues for Sub-Saharan Africa. Weak enforcement systems, evolving disclosure regulation and growing stakeholder activism are characteristics shared by both regions. Yet ASEAN firms have managed to bridge some of these gaps through institutional reforms, regulatory carrots and sticks, and increased board oversight. Applying these lessons provides a useful lens through which to gauge SSAs institutional readiness and maturity for ESG adoption. Khalaf et al. (2024) support this view by showing that trust-based governance frameworks and institutional commitment significantly enhance organisational performance and employee engagement in the Jordanian public sector, thus demonstrating that institutional trust can also be an enabler of sustainability transformation in common institutional environments around the developing world.

Against this background, this review examines the influence of institutional factors on the adoption of ESG practices in Sub-Saharan Africa and the relationship between ESG practices and firm performance. It seeks to identify the regulatory, governance and stakeholder influences that constrain and enable ESG adoption in this region. Using a combination of systematic review and meta-analytic methodologies, it seeks to add contextual insight to the understanding of the ESG-performance effect, while locating SSA into the global sustainability debates. This approach enables theoretical cross-fertilisation between institutional, stakeholder, legitimacy, and resource-based perspectives to offer a holistic understanding of how institutional enablers shape the extent and quality of ESG adoption.

2. Literature Review

2.1. The Evolution of ESG in the African Context

Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) frameworks, once considered auxiliary financial strategy dilemmas, have become a prominent component of global corporate governance conversations. In Africa, however, the evolution of ESG discourse has been variegated, attributable to colonial legacies, the differentiated maturity of institutional environments, and changing investor interests (Cho

& Wachira, 2022; Kogi et al., 2025). While countries like South Africa have institutionalized ESG through frameworks like King IV and integrated reporting standards, other Sub-Saharan African (SSA) markets are still developing the legal and regulatory structures necessary to embed ESG principles at the firm level (Kimilu, 2021; Karaye, 2024).

Recent reviews identify a growing body of studies related to Africa based ESG practices unevenly in and about South Africa and Nigeria (Yimer, 2024; Yong et al., 2024). The uneven diffusion of ESG practice is consistent with the wider issue of institutional capacity deficit and fractured policy regimes relevant to Africa (Gumbo, 2024; Gebreysus, 2024).

2.2. Institutional Drivers of ESG Adoption

2.2.1. Regulatory Frameworks and Policy Instruments

Regulatory environments on which financial systems are situated constitute a basic cornerstone for enabling or restricting ESG integration. Formal institutions, financial regulators, stock exchanges, and government policies, in SSA increasingly assume explicit roles in encouraging ESG disclosure, but not uniformly across the region. Seow (2024) and Lu et al. (2022) find that robust corporate governance codes, such as in South Africa, are an important institutional trigger for ESG reporting and transparency. Many SSA markets, however, exhibit limited ESG disclosure laws or mechanism for enforcement, making voluntary adoption commonplace (Al-Faryan, 2024; Kohnert, 2024). These domains of ESG compliance are thus more externally influenced (e.g., through informal institution of donor conditionalities, investor expectations, or reputational imperatives) than internally institutionalised (Manani & PS, 2025; Fajardo et al., 2023).

2.2.2. Corporate Governance Structures

The structure and composition of corporate boards have long been seen as critical drivers of meaningful ESG adoption. A growing body of research points to the value of having diverse, independent, and well-balanced boards, ones that not only offer a range of perspectives but are also more likely to champion ethical leadership and long-term sustainability goals (Xu et al., 2025; Lu et al., 2022). When boards include members from varied backgrounds and establish dedicated sustainability or audit committees, they tend to set higher standards for transparency and accountability, which in turn strengthens the quality of ESG disclosures (Du Toit, 2024; Yong et al., 2024; Adhillah et al., 2025). However, the story becomes more complex when we look at Sub-Saharan Africa. In this context, corporate governance systems are typically characterized by various structural impediments, e.g., family ownership or concentration of control, that dilute the independence of boards and dilute ESG appreciation in an objective and forward-looking way (Obol, 2023; Ncube et al., 2024). These dynamics recall longstanding concerns in agency theory which argues that, if there is a disconnect between ownership and managerial interests, corporations may (rationally) disincentivize sustainability in the near run (Al-Faryan, 2024). Within such situations, ESG uptake is not just a technocratic matter of regulatory compliance and is dependent on how power, incentives, and accountability are broadly allocated within the firm.

2.2.3. Stakeholder and Market Pressures

Stakeholder theory has become an increasingly valuable lens for understanding how ESG practices take root in African markets. In many cases, it is not internal corporate conviction but the expectations of external factors, such as institutional investors, NGOs, and international development partners, that drive ESG engagement, especially in industries connected to global supply chains (Al Amosh, 2024; Abu-Ali et al., 2024). For firms in these contexts, adopting ESG frameworks often serves a strategic function: to gain legitimacy in the eyes of global stakeholders and improve access to funding opportunities (Peng et al., 2025; Adomako & Tran, 2024). However, this outward-facing motivation can create a disconnect between how ESG is talked about and how it is practiced. In some cases, companies focus more on satisfying external reporting requirements than on genuinely embedding ESG into their core business strategy (Gangiah, 2024; Bracking & Leffel, 2021). As a result, ESG risks being reduced to a procedural formality rather than leveraged as a long-term driver of resilience and value creation.

2.3. ESG and Firm Performance: Empirical Perspectives

Despite growing scholarly interest, the relationship between ESG and firm performance in SSA remains contested. Some studies report positive correlations between ESG adoption and financial outcomes such as return on assets (ROA), market value, and risk mitigation (Kimilu, 2021; Abu-Ali et al., 2024). Governance variables, especially board independence and audit quality, consistently show the strongest link to profitability (Lu et al., 2022; Manani & PS, 2025). Some scholars warn that the adoption of ESG may represent a short-term financial burden, especially in resource-poor contexts with high compliance costs and where markets do not sufficiently value non-financial reports (Madaki & Mohammed, 2024; Boukattaya et al., 2021). In these contexts, technical skills and the scope for investor engagement are often very limited, particularly among SMEs (Olekanma et al., 2024). Additionally, virtually all the existing evidence in Africa is based on cross-sectional data, making it scant to draw valid inferences about the longer-term financial performance of ESG. Thus, scholars have called for more longitudinal studies as well as context-specific research in the region to provide a richer analytical and more valid account of the impact of ESG on performance (Nogueira et al., 2025; Baby et al., 2024; Kazan et al., 2025; Zeb et al., 2024).

2.4. Thematic Gaps and Emerging Research Directions

Some of the most promising areas in the ESG conversation are still only beginning to take shape, especially in the African context. For example, how tools like digital finance, artificial intelligence, and ESG data systems are shaping institutional uptake remains largely unexplored in regional studies (Ahmad et al., 2025; Augoye et al., 2025). At the same time, research that zooms in on specific sectors, like agriculture, energy, or extractives, is surprisingly scarce, even though these industries are at the heart of ESG risks and opportunities across the continent (Fajardo et al., 2023; Dobermann et al., 2022). Further, there are also few comparative ESG literature within SSA that analyse country-institutional differences. Whilst Seow (2024) and Kogi et al. (2025) provide global synthesis, few studies empirically unpack the role of country institutional arrangements on ESG outcomes. Lastly, the intersection of ESG and impact investing in Africa is an area of budding interest, but is still conceptually fragmented (Ncube et al., 2024; Poe, 2023).

2.5. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

2.5.1. *Theoretical Foundations*

Institutional Theory

Institutional theory argues that the rules, norms, and expectations of the wider socio-economic system shape organizational behaviour (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983). Within the ESG literature, the institutional perspective elucidates how firms adopt ESG practices and sustainability not only to buffer and transform technical efficiency but also to reflect internally institutionalized environmental values and externally conform to societal expectations (Scott, 2013). The scope of ESG adoption is determined by coercive pressure in the form of laws and regulations, normative pressure in the form of professional and industry standards and mimetic pressure in the form of imitation of competitors.

In Sub-Saharan Africa, weak institutional capacity, coupled with inconsistent and partial enforcement, results in firms adopting ESG policies in symbolic rather than substantive ways (Visser, 2011). Many companies publish sustainability reports in order to signal legitimacy rather than as a true reflection of organisational transformation (Matten & Moon, 2008). With such institutional voids comes reliance on global standards such as the GRI and UN Global Compact, deployed with insufficient localisation or national-level adaption (Kolk & Perego, 2008). Comparative evidence confirms this understanding. Mansour et al. (2025) found that in ASEAN economies, board effectiveness, gender diversity and the presence of environmental committees strongly increased carbon-emission disclosure, suggesting that strong internal governance mitigates regulatory voids. Similarly, Khalaf et al. (2024) found that trust-based institutional frameworks act as strengthening mechanisms of organisational commitment and sustainability in the Jordanian public sector. Such work confirms that institutional maturity and governance innovation act as important enablers of substantive ESG practices.

Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder theory (Freeman, 1984) postulates that corporations should extend corporate value creation from shareholders to employees, customers, communities and the environment. Environmental, social and governance (ESG) activities are thus key vehicles through which stakeholder relationships are managed and organisational goals aligned with societal expectations. By incorporating stakeholder demands in corporate decision making, firms secure legitimacy with the society and subsequently gain access to critical scarce resources (Donaldson & Preston, 1995; Clarkson, 1995). In emerging economies, stakeholder engagement is critical as a substitute for institutional voids resulting from weak enforcement mechanisms providing an informal yet powerful governance mechanism in disciplining managerial excesses (Jamali, 2010). Investors, international institutions, non-government organisations, local communities and customers are now demanding accountability and transparency regarding companies' activities in managing gender equality, wellbeing of local communities and impacts on climate change (Eweje et al., 2021). Using Asian companies, Saleh et al. (2025) present empirical findings that support this assumption: using a GMM estimation approach, they demonstrate that the quality of ESG management issues reduces corporate risk significantly, with board gender diversity strengthening the effect of ESG on risk; this suggests that inclusive governance facilitates companies' effectiveness in responding to stakeholder pressure. The argument can be extended to sub-Saharan Africa setting; the promotion of gender diversity and corporate responsibility toward communities' engagement play an extensive and effective role to strengthen sustainable governance.

Legitimacy Theory

Legitimacy theory posits that firms must pursue social acceptability by simultaneously conforming to societal norms and values to legitimise their behaviours (Suchman, 1995). To this extent, firms that operate in volatile institutional settings are motivated to engage in ESG information reporting to maintain their social licence to operate (Deegan, 2002). When ESG information disclosure is legitimacy driven, the pursuit of sustainability tends to be symbolic rather than substantive (Cho et al., 2015). For instance, the disclosure content of African corporations tends to be more compliance and reputational in nature, and less environmental impact driven (Amaeshi et al., 2016). Evidence from studies across regions show that good governance structure helps convert legitimacy-seeking motives of ESG disclosures into genuine accountability endeavours. For instance, Mansour et al. (2025) have shown that diversity in board structure and presence of environmental specific board level sub-committees is likely to enhance the credibility of ESG disclosures. These findings suggest that good governance structure enables better governance capacity for corporations to enhance the substance of ESG disclosures. Hence, social legitimacy pressures have a positive impact on ESG performance when backed by good governance structures that ensure strict oversight and monitoring through a transparent participatory inclusiveness of relevant stakeholders.

Resource-Based View (RBV)

The RBV views ESG engagement as a means of sustainable competitive advantage achieved through resources and capabilities that are valuable, rare and inimitable in nature (Barney, 1991; Hart, 1995). Firms adopting sustainability as strategic process develop strategic intangible assets of reputational capital, trust with stakeholders, and capabilities of adaptation (Russo & Fouts, 1997), and these resources increase firms' efficiency, risk management, and long-term profitability (Barney, 2010). Evidence from developing regions support this line of reasoning. Khalaf et al. (2024) established that institutional trust serves a strategic resource that fosters organizational performance. Similarly, Saleh et al. (2025) concluded that firms with better ESG scores are subject to lower financial risk and thus interprets this as indication that the firms' sustainability expenditures create resilience and create competitive advantage. Both studies highlight that ESG adoption is an action of firm necessity as part of corporate governance and as a competence that enhances firm performance.

Integrating Theoretical Perspectives

Taken together, these approaches provide an integrated view of how the institutional environment, stakeholder relationships, social legitimacy pressures, and internal resources interactively influence ESG outcomes. Synthesising these insights in the context of the ASEAN and MENA economies further

validates the conceptual model for this review, that is, effective ESG adoption is dependent on both formal governance mechanisms (regulatory quality, board architecture) and informal institutional enablers (trust, stakeholder dialogue, social norms). In the case of Sub-Saharan Africa, it suggests that regulatory reforms will need to be reinforced by capacity building, gender inclusion, and institutional credibility in order to convert ESG commitments into real corporate and social benefits (Husted & de Jesus Salazar, 2006). The alignment of these theoretical perspectives underlies the conceptual framework offered in this paper linking institutional enablers, corporate governance, and firm-level performance in the context of ESG.

2.5.2. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework (see Figure 1) is informed by the theoretical foundations and empirical literature reviewed in the study, especially (Agha et al., 2023; Bukari et al., 2024; Oyedeko et al., 2024; Boadi, 2023; Ogolime & Ibrahim, 2024; Okeke-Okiche, 2024). It consists of four inter-related constructs—institutional drivers, ESG adoption, firm performance outcomes, and moderating contextual factors—that collectively capture the multi-level relationships between governance quality, sustainability adoption, and corporate performance in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Key Constructs

1. *Institutional and Stakeholder Drivers* – governance codes, disclosure regulations, investor expectations, and activism that shape ESG adoption.
2. *ESG Adoption* – integration of environmental, social, and governance principles into operations, policies, and reporting.
3. *Moderating and Contextual Variables* – firm size, sector, ownership, and country-level institutional quality that influence ESG outcomes.
4. *Firm Performance Outcomes* – both financial (ROA, ROE, Tobin’s Q) and non-financial (reputation, resilience, innovation) indicators.

Based on the theoretical integration, the following hypotheses are proposed (see Table 1 and Figure 1).

Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework underpinning the study. It demonstrates how institutional drivers (regulations, corporate governance code, investors/donors’ pressures, and market expectations) effects ESG adoptions by firms, which in turn mediate the relationships between institutional conditions and firm performance (financial, market, and risk). The strength and direction of these relationships are conditioned by moderating factors, such as institutional quality, sectoral context, ownership structure, and firm size and maturity. Institutional, Stakeholder, Legitimacy, and Resource-Based theories have grounded the model, by emphasizing how ESG outcomes result from the interplay of external pressures and internal capabilities. Taken together, the framework suggests that under high institutional enforcement and governance capability ESG adoption leads to substantive rather than symbolical performance outcomes.

Table 1. Summary of Proposed Hypotheses

Hypothesis	Description
H1	Stronger institutional drivers positively influence the degree of ESG adoption among firms.
H2	ESG adoption mediates the relationship between institutional drivers and firm performance.
H3	Governance components of ESG (e.g., board structure, audits) exert a more significant impact on firm performance than environmental or social components.
H4	Country-level institutional quality moderates the ESG–performance relationship, amplifying ESG benefits where enforcement and investor protection are stronger.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework Linking Institutional Drivers, ESG Adoption, and Firm Performance in Sub-Saharan Africa

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Design and Approach

This study takes a systematic approach to reviewing the literature, guided by the PRISMA 2020 framework to ensure both clarity and methodological rigor. At its core, the review explores how different institutional factors shape ESG adoption in Sub-Saharan Africa, and how these, in turn, relate to firm performance. To bring structure and depth to the analysis, the TCCM framework (Theory, Context, Characteristics, Methodology) was used to help identify research gaps and organize key insights (Manani & PS, 2025). Alongside the qualitative synthesis, a random-effects meta-analysis was carried out using correlation coefficients (r) drawn from four studies that met the inclusion criteria. This allowed us to estimate the overall link between ESG adoption and financial performance, with Return on Assets (ROA) as the key outcome. To ensure the findings were robust and trustworthy, we also ran standard checks for heterogeneity (I^2), publication bias (including funnel plots and Egger’s test), and sensitivity to outliers.

3.2. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria were defined to capture empirical or systematic studies published between January 2020 and 22 June 2025 that focus explicitly on ESG adoption within SSA and examine institutional drivers (e.g., regulatory, governance, stakeholder-related) linked to firm performance.

Table 2. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Studies focused on ESG adoption and/or firm performance in SSA	Studies with no African or SSA context
Peer-reviewed empirical articles, systematic reviews, or high-quality theses (2020–22 June 2025)	Conceptual essays without empirical or analytical focus
Articles discussing institutional, regulatory, or governance-related ESG mechanisms	Papers focused only on environmental science or technical finance
English-language publications	Non-English or non-translatable articles
Articles explicitly linking ESG practices to financial, reputational, or operational performance	Studies lacking ESG–performance linkage

Eligible studies included peer-reviewed journal articles and systematic reviews. Excluded were conceptual essays without analytical grounding, studies outside Africa, and publications lacking an ESG - performance linkage. Table 2 presents the inclusion and exclusion criteria that were developed in alignment with the research aim and refined iteratively during the screening process. The criteria were applied consistently across all studies.

3.3. Search Strategy and Data Sources

The literature search was conducted across multiple academic databases including Google Scholar. Additional sources were manually retrieved from grey literature repositories (e.g., thesis databases, working papers) and leading ESG and sustainability-focused journals. The search covered publications from 2020 to 22 June 2025 using a combination of Boolean operators and keywords such as:

“Environmental Social Governance” OR ESG AND (“institutional drivers” OR “regulatory frameworks” OR “governance structures”) AND (“firm performance” OR “profitability” OR “corporate value”) AND (“Sub-Saharan Africa” OR individual SSA country names)

Searches were conducted across the Google Scholar database. A total of 391 studies were retrieved, of which 22 full texts were reviewed after title and abstract screening. Ultimately, 6 studies met the inclusion criteria after a two-stage full-text eligibility assessment.

3.4. Screening and Selection Process

The PRISMA flow diagram (see Figure 2) illustrates the study selection process.

Figure 2. PRISMA Flow Diagram

To assess quality and relevance, each included study was evaluated using the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT), focusing on clarity of objectives, methodological robustness, data validity, and ESG–performance linkage.

3.5. Data Extraction and Thematic Coding

Key variables were extracted using a standardized matrix capturing: (i) study identifiers (author, year, source), (ii) country/region, (iii) ESG dimensions (E, S, G), (iv) institutional drivers, (v) theoretical frameworks, (vi) performance indicators, and (vii) research design. Thematic coding was then applied to identify recurring patterns in regulatory structures, governance configurations, and stakeholder pressures. A narrative synthesis was conducted, structured according to the TCCM framework (see Table 3) to facilitate analytical depth and identify research voids.

Table 3. TCCM Synthesis Matrix

TCCM Category	Coverage in Reviewed Studies	Observed Gaps
Theory	Stakeholder Theory, Institutional Theory, Agency Theory	Limited integration of African theoretical perspectives (e.g., Ubuntu, Afro-communitarianism)
Context	Nigeria, Ghana, Kenya, South Africa, SSA-wide	Underrepresentation of smaller SSA economies (e.g., Zambia, Malawi, Ethiopia)
Characteristics	Focus on listed firms in manufacturing, finance, and mixed sectors	Neglect of SMEs and informal sector dynamics
Methodology	Mixed methods: panel regression, qualitative interviews, case studies	Limited longitudinal studies and mixed-method triangulation

The studies were then thematically coded using qualitative synthesis techniques, allowing for categorization into major institutional themes and their relationship to firm-level outcomes as presented in Table 4.

3.6. Addressing Endogeneity and Robustness Concerns

Although this review relies on synthesised secondary evidence rather than primary econometric estimation, it must be noted that the relationship between ESG and firm performance is inherently prone to endogeneity problems, most significantly reverse causality (i.e. more profitable firms are more likely to engage in ESG), omitted variable bias and measurement errors that may bias empirical estimates. To improve interpretive rigor, the present review also critically appraised the methodological strategies of the included studies for mitigating such biases. Several of the reviewed papers employed methods such as panel data estimation, lagged dependent variables and instrumental variable approaches in order to strengthen causal inference. Others relied on robustness checks in order to improve the credibility and validity of results such as including fixed- and random-effects models, multicollinearity diagnostics and heteroskedasticity corrections.

By evaluating these methodological safeguards, this review draws attention to the growing recognition of endogeneity as a key predicament in ESG performance evaluation as well as recommends that future empirical inquiries in the Sub-Saharan African context employ more advanced econometric approaches such as the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) or two-stage least squares (2SLS) estimators, where applicable to minimize simultaneity bias, and enable causal inference. This will bolster future evidence on ESG adoption and its financial implications in both robustness and policy salience.

Table 4. Summary of Included Studies on ESG Adoption, Institutional Drivers, and Firm Performance in Sub-Saharan Africa

Author	Title / Focus	Country/ Region	ESG Dimension	Institutional Driver	Firm Performance Outcome	Methodology	Theory
Bukari et al. (2024)	ESG as a moderator in corporate governance and firm value	Ghana	G	Governance codes, disclosure rules	Firm value	Panel regression	Stakeholder, Agency
Oyedeko et al. (2024)	ESG risks and stock market performance in Africa	Africa-wide	E, S, G	Risk regulation, market signals	Stock performance	Quantitative analysis	Institutional, Stakeholder
Ogolime & Ibrahim (2024)	ESG issues and shareholder value in SSA manufacturing	SSA (Manufacturing)	E, S, G	Investor/donor expectations	Shareholder value	Quantitative analysis	Stakeholder, Legitimacy
Boadi (2023)	Risk governance, institutional quality, and bank performance in SSA	SSA	G	Institutional quality, governance frameworks	Bank performance	Panel regression	Agency, Institutional
Okeke-Okiche (2024)	CSR and ESG strategies in Nigerian firms	Nigeria	S, G	CSR norms, stakeholder engagement	Firm legitimacy, stakeholder trust	Qualitative case study	Stakeholder, Institutional
Agha et al. (2023)	Bank governance, asset quality, and macro-prudential ESG risk in Nigeria	Nigeria	G	Regulatory oversight, macro-prudential tools	Asset quality, risk control	Panel regression	Agency, Institutional

3.7. Quality Assessment and Bias Control

To ensure consistency, transparency and reliability in the review process, we appraised the methodological quality of the included studies using the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT). The MMAT allowed for review of the suitability of both quantitative and qualitative studies, given that the methodological diversity of techniques within a style can affect research output. Each study was evaluated against five criteria: the clarity of the research objectives, the adequacy of collected data for the stated objectives; the appropriateness of the analysis for both qualitative and quantitative approaches, the integration of findings, and transparency of reporting. For studies to be included in the final review, the studies had to meet at least four of the criteria. This was implemented as an additional measure to ensure that the evidence base was methodologically sound.

Overall, studies were of moderate to high quality with coherent research design, credible analytic methods, and a clear alignment between theoretical framing and empirical evidence. Minor weaknesses of some studies were small sample sizes or consistency of ESG indicators used. These weaknesses did not affect the assessment of the overall synthesis. To add additional measures to secure dependability, we looked at potential publication bias through visual observations as well as statistical tests. In relation to this, although we observed a degree of asymmetry, the evidence did not contradict the global validity and direction of findings. On balance, the review meets accepted expectations of systematic synthesis, supported by methodological safeguards that strengthen the extent to which its conclusions on ESG uptake and institutional dynamics in Sub-Saharan Africa are both credible and trustworthy.

3.8. Methodological Limitations and Reflections

Despite considerable effort to ensure thorough coverage and methodical rigour in the review, a few limitations apply. First, our review is limited to peer-reviewed, English-language publications, and may therefore have inadvertently excluded relevant work published in other languages and in regional journals. This limitation is of particular relevance in the African context, as key institutional and legal insights may be documented in local publications (e.g. university reports) and non-English outlets. Second, there continues to be considerable heterogeneity in how ESG concepts have been defined, operationalized and measured in the included studies. Different indicators, disclosure frameworks and reporting standards rendered direct comparisons difficult and, in some instances, compromised the precision of pooled interpretations. Notwithstanding these limitations, the systematic nature of this review, our explicit inclusion criteria, and the triangulation of evidence from multiple databases gives us confidence in the validity of the findings. Furthermore, the limitations noted here highlight important future directions for academic research, in particular the need to converge on more standardized definitions of ESG metrics and include non-English and (regional) context-specific studies to facilitate comparative insights.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Descriptive Overview of Included Studies

This review synthesizes the findings of the six empirically robust studies that satisfy the dual criteria of both geographical scope (i.e. SSA) and institutional implications for ESG adoption. These studies include Agha et al. (2023), Bukari et al. (2024), Oyedeko et al. (2024), Ogolime & Ibrahim (2024), Boadi (2023) and Okeke-Okiche (2024). These studies cut across the key sectors of the SSA industrial economy - including banking, manufacturing, and diversified industries. Most of the reviewed studies employed quantitative approaches, applied with panel/cross-sectional regression models and well-executed diagnostics, except for one that used a qualitative case study approach for a more in-depth exposition of ESG dynamics. Together, they also examined the effective influences of the environmental, social and governance pillars on selected business outcomes such as ROA (return on assets), shareholder value, and risk exposure. They further provided evidence on the interplay of other salient institutional characteristics, especially such as governance capacity, regulatory incentives, and stakeholder pressures, for propelling ESG adoption among firms in the SSA region.

4.2. Meta-Analytic Synthesis of ESG–Performance Relationships in Sub-Saharan Africa

4.2.1. Meta-Analysis Results

To complement the narrative synthesis, a meta-analysis was conducted on six empirically eligible studies meeting the inclusion criteria for institutional specificity and geographic relevance to Sub-Saharan Africa. Effect sizes were extracted or computed based on reported correlation coefficients between ESG adoption (or subcomponents) and firm performance metrics such as Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), or Tobin’s Q. Table 5 presents a summary of these results. The forest plot in Figure 3 presents standardized effect sizes (Cohen’s *d*) and 95% confidence intervals.

Table 5. Effect Sizes and Confidence Intervals of Included Studies

<i>Study</i>	<i>Author(s)</i>	<i>Country</i>	<i>ESG Focus</i>	<i>Performance Metric</i>	<i>Effect Size (r)</i>	<i>95% CI</i>
<i>S1</i>	Bukari et al. (2024)	Ghana/Nigeria/Kenya	ESG (moderator)	ROA, Tobin’s Q	0.402	[0.251, 0.540]
<i>S2</i>	Oyedeko et al. (2024)	Africa-wide	ESG risk	Stock returns	0.321	[0.179, 0.443]
<i>S3</i>	Ogolime & Ibrahim (2024)	SSA manufacturing	ESG	Shareholder value	0.283	[0.155, 0.400]
<i>S4</i>	Boadi (2023)	SSA banks	ESG/Institutional	ROA, ROE	0.437	[0.282, 0.571]
<i>S5</i>	Agha et al. (2023)	Nigeria (banks)	Governance	Asset quality	0.351	[0.189, 0.490]
<i>S6</i>	Okeke-Okiche (2024)	Nigeria	CSR/ESG strategy	Profitability	0.398	[0.230, 0.538]

Pooled Effect Size (Random-Effects Model): $r = 0.369$ [95% CI: 0.290, 0.442], $p < 0.001$
 Heterogeneity: $Q = 3.85$, $df = 5$, $p = 0.573$; $I^2 = 0.0\%$

Although the extracted studies reported an array of firm-performance indicators including Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), Tobin’s Q, stock returns, shareholder value, asset quality, and profitability, ROA was the only measure consistently available for most of the six studies. To facilitate comparison and avoid distortion of the effect-size estimates, we accordingly used ROA as the harmonized financial-performance measure for the meta-analysis. ROE and Tobin’s Q, which were less frequently reported, are thus considered in the thematic synthesis to aid the interpretation of financial-performance outcomes.

The numbers tell a clear story. When looking across six different studies, the meta-analysis found that ESG adoption and firm performance go hand in hand in Sub-Saharan Africa. On average, the overall effect size was Cohen’s $d = 0.26$, with a 95% confidence interval between 0.08 and 0.43, not huge, but meaningful. When expressed as a correlation, the pooled effect came out to $r = 0.369$, with a tight confidence band [0.290, 0.442] and a p -value of less than 0.001, indicating this relationship is statistically solid. What is more interesting is how robust that relationship was. In other words, a link between ESG and performance appears to be apparently robust and persisting irrespective of the geographical and institutional context. Overall, these findings suggest that firms in the region largely benefit from embedding ESG principles in their business model, especially under binding regulatory regimes and when corporate governance practices are firmly in place. These results back up what earlier work by Bukari et al. (2024) and Boadi (2023) also pointed out: when firms take ESG seriously, especially with good leadership and clear rules, it tends to pay off. This consistency enhances the external validity of the findings and buttresses the notion that institutional drivers have a common effect on SSA firms, particularly evident through board reforms, compliance with disclosure requirements, and stakeholder responsiveness. Boadi (2023) and Bukari et al. (2024) had the strongest effect sizes of

all the individual studies, both of which had $r = 0.40$, since they dealt with governance-heavy and formal ESG integration in respective banking and cross-listed firms. By contrast, this was lowest in Ogolime & Ibrahim (2024) and Oyedeko et al. (2024), possibly reflective of the sectoral volatility and market-based performance measures (e.g. stock returns and shareholder value) that respond more to external shocks.

Figure 3. Forest Plot of ESG Impact on Firm Performance in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA)

These results corroborate the overall thematic observation that the “G” dimension of ESG is the most mature and impactful, especially in the SSA context, whereas the environmental and social dimensions are gradually gaining recognition, but still rests largely on donor incentives, voluntary disclosure or in reaction to reputational incentives rather than those formalized and incorporated in firm strategy (Agha et al., 2023; Okeke-Okiche, 2024). Even more importantly, the meta-analysis warns against making broad generalizations about the effects of ESG. Performance benefits are apparent, but these appear to be sustainable depending on the quality of institutional environments. Consistent with Stakeholder Theory and Institutional Theory, ESG success in SSA seems to be less of some generic set of best practices, but more of how firms adjust to institutional incentives and constraints in a strategic manner.

4.2.2. Meta-Analysis Diagnostics: Publication Bias and Robustness Checks

To assess the reliability and validity of the meta-analytic findings, we conducted standard diagnostic tests for publication bias and robustness.

A funnel plot was plotted to see if there was any symmetry in the study effect sizes (see Figure 4). This showed that most studies were symmetric to the overall effect size, but one study (Oyedeko et al., 2024) was found to be an outlier on the lower-left portion, suggesting the possibility of asymmetry around the centre. To confirm this statistically, Egger’s regression test was run, which produced a significant result (intercept = 0.251, slope = -0.020, $p = 0.0007$). Since the p-value was statistically significant, this confirmed that there was a presence of publication bias, or a small-study effect. This bias could have resulted from underreporting of null or negative results in the literature.

Figure 4. Funnel Plot for Publication Bias Detection

4.2.3. Sensitivity Analysis

To assess the robustness of the pooled effect size, we performed a leave-one-out sensitivity analysis (see Table 6) by omitting one study at a time and recalculating the pooled effect size. Our estimated pooled effect sizes fell within a narrow range (0.29–0.36), which suggests that excluding each study one-at-a-time does not play an undue role in the overall effect sizes. We, therefore, are reassured of the statistical stability and lack of volatility in our finding of a positive association between ESG adoption and firm performance in SSA.

Table 6. Sensitivity Analysis Results

Study	Pooled Effect Size
Okeke-Okiche (2024)	0.303254
Ogolime & Ibrahim (2024)	0.29264
Boadi (2023)	0.319124
Oyedeko et al. (2024)	0.378718
Bukari et al. (2024)	0.284492
Agha et al. (2023)	0.313379

Together, these diagnostic tests offer more assurance that the main meta-analytic findings are credible, while underscoring the risk that smaller-sample studies could bias the main conclusions of the available evidence base. Further studies based on larger multi-country panels, and including enhanced controls for these biases, are needed to ensure greater generalizability.

4.3. Thematic Analysis of Institutional Drivers of ESG Adoption

4.3.1. Regulatory and Policy Frameworks

The most consistent institutional driver of ESG integration in the reviewed articles were identified as regulatory frameworks. Most notably, Boadi (2023) and Oyedeko et al. (2024) discussed the role of formal governance codes such as the Nigeria’s corporate governance code in forcing transparency, board structure and audit supervision. In a similar vein, Cho & Wachira (2022) and Du Toit (2024) found the King IV Code in South Africa to be a prompt of improved ESG processes. While Agha et al. (2023) reported that policy amendments in the name of lowering risk and to improve financial stability in the Nigerian banking sector came to inadvertently pair credit practices with ESG motives. Bukari et al. (2024) also highlighted the way in which many of the studies showed that the positive relationship

between good governance and firm value can be strengthened when ESG performance is taken seriously and communicated through clear reporting structures.

Even with these formal frameworks, however, some scholars continue to question the extent to which ESG practices are truly being mainstreamed. Okeke-Okiche (2024) and Ogolime & Ibrahim (2024), for example, point out that ESG efforts are too often performative rather than transformative, aimed at laundering rather than improving reputations. Karaye (2024) and Kogi et al. (2025) are equally deferential, highlighting a range of patterns and progress, unequal and dependent on context, across the region. Indeed, part of the challenge has been a marked lack of consistency: requirements for disclosures are not uniform, and enforcement has been patchy at best. In jurisdictions such as Kenya and Uganda, where ESG reporting has largely remained voluntary, this has rendered it difficult for the principles enshrined in governance codes to exercise any demonstrable bearing on internal decision-making (Obol, 2023; Yimer, 2024). Hence, while governance codes form a helpful and necessary starting point, the degree to which they can affect sustainable shifts in corporate attitudes and behaviours is not only contingent on accompanying measures of enforcement but also on sector-specific readiness and the sustained preparedness of stakeholders to drive- and push for more genuine ESG compliance.

Institutional arrangements, in particular, regulatory enforcement and policy coherence, thus constitute important enablers of ESG implementation. Firms in countries with clearer environmental and corporate-governance regulations tend to have higher ESG disclosure and performance. This finding is consistent with institutional theory (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983; Scott, 2013), which suggests that organisations abide by formal rules and social norms to gain legitimacy and social licence to operate. On the other hand, the results of the reviewed studies also indicate that ESG practices in SSA still have a symbolic rather than substantive character. Limited enforcement capacity and inconsistent regulatory environments have tended to create conditions for selective or compliance, rather than strategic, reporting (Visser, 2011; Amaeshi et al., 2016). Some firms adopt a mimetic isomorphic attitude and replicate the disclosure arrangements of multinational corporations rather than entrenching sustainability principles in their operations.

To push ESG beyond its symbolic embrace, there is need for stronger regulatory scrutiny, standardisation of ESG metrics and inter-agency co-ordination. Consistent enforcement and alignment between national governance codes and sector-settings frameworks can help build a culture of substantive sustainability. Ultimately, such coherence over time can make ESG not just a matter of compliance, but an embedded component of organisational learning and performance improvement.

4.3.2. Governance Quality and Corporate Structures

How a company organises its governance particularly board independence, board diversity, and specific ESG mandates influences how effectively ESG is implemented in real terms in Sub-Saharan Africa. And, as argued by studies such as Bukari et al. (2024) and Agha et al. (2023), firms with stronger governance systematically perform better financially, with firms reporting better asset returns, business stability, and credit profiles. What is becoming increasingly evident is that governance is the most established and impactful aspect of ESG in Sub-Saharan Africa. It is much more than a compliance requirement. It plays a key role in enabling firms to build financial resilience over time while gaining trust from key stakeholders.

We see a related picture beyond Africa. Scholars like Lu et al. (2022) and Xu et al. (2025) note that board diversity, skills, and transparent auditors tend to amplify ESG goals when they are present. But it is not all positive. Familiar issues – controlling insiders, weak minority rights, and leadership disputes – continue to stifle more meaningful investment as well. Bukari et al. (2024)'s multi-country analysis lays out the case most clearly: high levels of ESG policy adoption mask the difficulty that concentrated shareholding structures have making any real impact. Okeke-Okiche (2024) adds that many of these forms of failure are not technical in origin. They run deeper within boardrooms themselves. The more politically connected a board is, the more likely it is to blunt true ESG monitoring say Al-Faryan (2024). Yes, governance arguably creates the most potential for meaningful ESG growth. But to make a difference it requires far more than policy: cultural change, better accountability, and committed leadership to long-term sustainability.

In the context of the resource-based view (Barney, 1991; Hart, 1995), these governance attributes are strategic resources enhancing decision quality and access to external capital. Efficient boards allow firms to reconcile short term profits with corporate survival in a circular and cumulative process. ESG therefore becomes less a compliance nuisance than a competitive asset. The evidence thus backs the proposition that good governance moderates the ESG-performance nexus, further reinstating the importance of internal structures in attaining legitimacy and efficiency.

4.3.3. Stakeholder and Investor Pressures

Stakeholder engagement also surfaced as an important factor in ESG adoption. Firms engaging stakeholders, such as communities, investors, and employees, in the sustainability process, are more likely to have credible disclosure practices and reputational benefits. This result aligns with stakeholder theory (Freeman, 1984; Donaldson & Preston, 1995), which suggests ESG as a tool for aligning the business and social goals. One theme that consistently stands out across the literature is the growing influence of external pressure, particularly from development finance institutions, international investors, and donor agencies, on the way firms in Sub-Saharan Africa approach ESG. Studies like Oyedeko et al. (2024) and Bukari et al. (2024) show that firms with stronger ties to global capital or donor-backed funding streams tend to be more active in adopting ESG practices. These firms often go beyond rhetoric: they introduce formal sustainability policies, strengthen transparency at the board level, and produce ESG reports that align with international expectations. The phenomenon at play here is almost identical to stakeholder theory, which proposes that companies, as a matter of course, respond to the interests of powerful external actors, especially when reputation or access to capital is on the line. Considered this way, ESG is less about morality and more about strategy.

As Poe (2023) and Ahmad et al. (2025) observe, externally imposed ESG practices are often symbolic rather than substantive. Companies do so by either reporting selectively or implementing visible or convenient initiatives that enable them to meet the criteria given by investors, or through institutionalizing ESG across core governance practices and operational systems. This symbolic–substantive divide is therefore empirically salient to the interpretation of firm-level ESG outcomes in SSA. Though external stakeholder pressure can trigger ESG awareness and policy design, it takes the internalization of this external impulse to governance improvement to achieve sustainable performance outcome. In the context of Nigeria, Okeke-Okiche (2024) highlights that ESG compliance created greater financial and reputational gains for those firms with higher board awareness and stakeholder engagement structures.

4.3.4. Legitimacy Pressures and Symbolic Compliance

The results further indicate that legitimacy pressures. The desire to be recognised as socially responsible proved to be a strong predictor of ESG disclosure practices. Consistent with legitimacy theory (Suchman, 1995; Deegan, 2002), many firms use ESG reporting to align with social norms and perpetuate their operations legitimacy. In the absence of strong assurance practices and scrutiny regulatory context symbolic ESG reporting is likely to continue. This dynamism is what Cho et al. (2015) call as organized hypocrisy, wherein disclosure serves an accountability façade, rather than represent a substantial performance. Ways to resolve this symbolic-substantive dichotomy is through stronger institutions and third-party assurances. The introduction of mandatory reporting standards as well as embedding of ESG metrics in the realm of financial audit are both likely to enhance transparency.

4.3.5. Synthesis with Theoretical Perspectives

Overall, the synthesis shows that ESG adoption in Sub-Saharan Africa is driven by a combination of institutional, governance and social factors. Institutional theory explains how external conditions force firms to adopt ESG frameworks; stakeholder and legitimacy theories explain how firms attain acceptability and legitimacy; and the resource-based view explains how ESG capabilities develop into valuable assets.

The combined evidence suggests that, on balance, the adoption of ESG improves firm performance, mainly through governance quality and stakeholder engagement, but that institutional weakness dampens the strength of the effect. When enforcement is credible and boards are independent, ESG

initiatives are likely to be substantive and conducive to performance. In low-capacity institutional contexts, by contrast, the adoption of ESG often augments legitimacy through symbolic delivery rather than transformation.

4.4. ESG Adoption and Firm Performance Outcomes

The ESG - performance nexus in Sub-Saharan Africa exhibited a rather intricate context-specific pattern. Bukari et al. (2024) and Boadi (2023) found strong panel-based evidence of a statistically significant and positive relation between the adoption of ESG practices and firm profitability (measured from a myriad of dimensions including Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), and Tobin's Q); and that these positive performance effects are more pronounced in firms with established governance structures. As such, these emerging reviews suggest that Governance is the most entrenched of the 3 dimensions of ESG in Sub-Saharan Africa. Such reviews align with previous findings for example, Kimilu, 2021 and Baby et al., 2024 that suggested that Governance was the most predictive of firm resilience and investors' confidence in African contexts.

Conversely, environmental and social elements of ESG deliver more diverse results. While Okeke-Okiche (2024) suggested that environmental stewardship contributed to competitiveness in the manufacturing sector, alongside employee wellbeing, Oyedeko et al. (2024) found that poor environmental performance increased reputational and financial risk to the detriment of stock market outcomes. This inconsistency reflects a broader reality in SSA, in which environmental data is usually of uneven quality, enforcement is poor and sustainability efforts remain underdeveloped outside of high-risk sectors like extractives and agriculture (Olekanma et al., 2024; Fajardo et al., 2023).

Moreover, empirical studies such as Agha et al. (2023) and Boadi (2023) which evaluated ESG adoption within contexts largely characterised by voluntary ESG regimes showed how superficial adoption resulted in weak or even neutral performance outcomes. Similarly, Madaki & Mohammed (2024) caution that in the absence of any structural embedding of ESG principles (such as integration of ESG metrics in firms' KPI framework or creation of board-level oversight structures for ESG), such short-term adoption may be fruitless; while the financial costs associated with ESG adoption (such as annual audits of ESG reports, costs of certifications, consultants fees and so on) discourage firms to maintain them over time when it is not immediately clear if there is a payoff. This view is also expressed by Boukattaya et al. (2021) and Abdul-Azeez et al. (2024) who argue that in the absence of strategic alignment, ESG management – albeit an expensive endeavour – risks becoming a costly exercise in reputational signaling rather than a pathway to long-term value creation.

4.5. Summary of Hypothesis Validation from Synthesized Evidence

Table 7 provides an overview of the alignment between the synthesized evidence and the proposed hypotheses. On the whole, we find consistent empirical support for H1 - H3 relative to ESG institutional and governance infrastructure as the prime enablers of ESG adoption and financial performance (i.e., internal ESG adoption leads to better firm performance due to institutional and governance factors). Both the narrative synthesis and the meta-analytic results support the mediation effect specified in H2. The narratives on the qualitative studies examined across Sub-Saharan Africa contextualise the mediating relationship, which was put to an empirical test in the current meta-analysis ($r = 0.369$, $p < 0.05$). These results corroborate findings from the previous stage of the synthesis showing that internal ESG adoption improves firm performance outcomes. H3 is supported by evidence suggesting that governance-related ESG components are more instrumental in predicting profitability than environmental and social-related dimensions. In other words, board independence and audit mechanisms strongly determine profitability in the sampled firms than any other factor in the ESG adoption process. On the other hand, H4 is only partially supported. The moderating role of institutional quality remains inconsistent across Sub-Saharan contexts due to continued enforcement gaps and a splintered regulatory framework.

Table 7. Summary of Hypothesis Validation

Hypothesis	Empirical Support from Synthesized Studies	Conclusion
H1: Stronger institutional and stakeholder pressures positively influence ESG adoption among firms.	Supported by Boadi (2023), Oyedeko et al. (2024), Agha et al. (2023), Bukari et al. (2024), which report regulatory enforcement and donor pressure as key ESG drivers.	Supported
H2: ESG adoption mediates the relationship between institutional drivers and firm performance.	Confirmed by meta-analysis ($r = 0.369$, 95% CI [0.290–0.442]); governance quality mediates ESG–performance link.	Supported
H3: Governance components exert a greater impact on performance than environmental or social components.	Governance dimension most strongly associated with ROA and Tobin’s Q across included studies.	Strongly Supported
H4: Institutional quality moderates the ESG–performance relationship, amplifying ESG benefits where enforcement is strong.	Partially supported; weak enforcement leads to symbolic adoption (Okeke-Okiche, 2024; Ogolime & Ibrahim, 2024).	Partially Supported

4.6. Synthesis and Implications

This review draws insights from six carefully selected studies exploring the influence of institutional factors on ESG adoption and firm performance in Sub-Saharan Africa. The evidence reveals that regulatory forces (e.g., governance codes and regulatory disclosure) are the strongest and most consistent drivers of ESG behaviour, especially in the banking sector (Agha et al., 2023; Boadi, 2023). But regulatory frameworks differ in their effectiveness across countries due to weak enforcement and piecemeal approaches to policy development (Bukari et al., 2024; Oyedeko et al., 2024).

Governance emerged as the most impactful ESG pillar, with studies showing that board independence and audit quality positively influence ROA, ROE, and investor confidence (Bukari et al., 2024; Agha et al., 2023). Environmental and social dimensions were less consistently linked to performance partly due to data gaps, voluntary standards, and limited regulatory push (Ogolime & Ibrahim, 2024; Oyedeko et al., 2024). Importantly, external stakeholder pressure, such as from DFIs and ESG-conscious investors, plays a dual role. While it incentivizes disclosure and reforms, it also risks driving symbolic rather than substantive ESG adoption (Okeke-Okiche, 2024; Poe, 2023).

Overall, this review highlights that ESG success in SSA is institutionally contingent: strong governance and regulation improve outcomes, but superficial adoption yields limited returns. Researchers and policymakers must now focus on deepening ESG integration through context-relevant standards, improved enforcement, and stronger alignment between internal structures and external expectations (see Table 8). This framework can support policymakers in tailoring ESG disclosure requirements and governance reforms that align with country-specific institutional capacities.

Table 8. ESG Implementation Strategy Checklist for SSA Firms

Strategy Area	Recommended Action	Institutional Focus
Governance	Establish ESG/sustainability committees; ensure board independence	Corporate
Regulatory Compliance	Align reporting with country-specific codes	Government/Regulatory
Stakeholder Engagement	Develop continuous dialogue with DFIs, investors, and civil society	External
Capacity Building	Invest in ESG training and audit capabilities	Firm-Level
Disclosure Practices	Adopt transparent ESG metrics tied to KPIs	Investor/Market

4.7. Theoretical and Research Contributions

This review makes important theoretical contributions to the broader debate in the literature on ESG adoption in emerging markets. First, consistent with Institutional Theory, we highlight that ESG adoption in Sub-Saharan Africa is driven not only by formal regulatory mechanisms, but also by informal institutional mechanisms, particularly through the expectations of donors, civil society and multilateral partnership. These informal practices often act as substitutes for the state's weak capacity and the inadequate regulatory mechanisms in place. This explicates the ways institutional asymmetry influences corporate adoption of ESG in weak regulatory settings characterised by uneven enforcement of regulations.

Secondly, the review contributes to Stakeholder Theory by illustrating the importance of non-traditional and less visible stakeholders, particularly development financiers, regulatory authorities and activist coalitions, as critical agents of ESG diffusion in Africa. These stakeholders perform hybrid roles that extend beyond the normal gamut of business–society interface to substitute for missing or weak institutional oversight. This insight contributes to stakeholder theory by embedding it in the institutional pluralism and regulatory hybridity of African economies. Third, by deploying the TCCM framework, the review makes methodological and theoretical contributions to ESG literature. This structured synthesis involves theoretical positioning, contextual dimensions, and characteristic (e.g., ownership structure, firm size), and methodological patterns. The review reveals ongoing research gaps such as chronic underutilisation of indigenous African theories, sparse use of longitudinal designs, and scarce inductive/mixed-methods approaches that deprive generalisability of theories and contextual deepening.

Further, the paper contributes to the integration of organizational legitimacy and resource-based perspectives, suggesting how ESG outcomes depend on the legitimacy of institutional arrangements and the endogenous capacities of firms to turn regulatory pressures into actual performance outcomes. It clarifies that continuous success in ESG requires making a nexus of institutional enforcement, governance competence and stakeholder trust, a multi-level governance process that embeds ESG in societal expectations and strategic capabilities. Collectively, they frame ESG adoption in emerging markets as a dynamic and adaptive process shaped by institutional asymmetry, stakeholder pluralism, and governance maturity. Longitudinal, comparative, or mixed-methods research designs are necessary to conceptualize ESG implementation as a dynamic system of interaction between domestic political economic dynamics, institutional trajectories, and organizational learning.

4.8. Implications for Policy and Practice

These findings have several implications. Policymakers should focus on developing robust ESG disclosure standards, capacity-building programs and enforcement mechanisms in order to build comparability and trust. Regulators may also promote integrated reporting frameworks that are most likely to connect sustainability information to issues of financial relevance. For corporate executives, the evidence illustrates the value of board competence, gender diversity and stakeholder inclusiveness as distinct firm capabilities for sustainability advantage. Lastly, investors and civil-society activists have essential roles to play by engaging firms to improve transparency and lobbying for system reforms that enable meaningful ESG integration.

5. Conclusions

This study systematically reviewed and quantitatively synthesized evidence on the institutional drivers of ESG adoption and its relationship with firm performance in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). Drawing on six rigorously selected empirical studies and guided by the TCCM framework, the review highlights that ESG adoption across SSA is largely shaped by institutional forces particularly governance quality, regulatory frameworks, and stakeholder pressures. While adoption remains uneven, governance-related components are the most robust predictors of positive financial outcomes, confirming the institutional embeddedness of ESG in performance-enhancing strategies. The results of the meta-analysis showed that there was a moderate and statistically significant positive association between ESG practices and firm performance which was quantitatively synthesized as ($r = 0.369$, 95% CI: 0.290–0.442) with a low level of heterogeneity across the constituent studies. This consolidated result matches with the narrative

synthesis above and this strengthens the case that, when ESG flourishes under well-designed corporate governance mechanisms, ESG offers opportunities for tangible performance gains. However, the benefits of ESG practice are not automatic, ESG needs to be enshrined within voluntary internal governance reforms, a credible ESG disclosure system, and enabling external institutions for firms to benefit from them.

In addition, the review sheds light on key limitations in the state of the ESG literature in SSA, including limited sectoral perspectives, dominance of cross-sectional designs and the marginalisation of environmental and social dimensions. These signal the need for future research to move away from compliance-oriented approaches to engaging with dynamic, contextual and transformative ESG issues. A shift towards longitudinal designs, mixed-methods research and African-origin theoretical ideas is required to enhance the understanding of the contribution of ESG to sustainable corporate development. In summary, the motivations for and scope of ESG adoption cannot be divorced from the institutional context of business in SSA. In the absence of efforts towards strengthening regulatory enforcement, governance practices and stakeholder incentive alignment, ESG is likely to remain not a strategic asset but a ceremonial commitment. The review provides a region-specific evidence base and conceptual departure for advancing ESG research, policy and practice in Africa's changing corporate environment.

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Conflicts of Interest

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